

Global Variance Reduction with TRIPOLI-4[®] using the MAGIC method and the AMS algorithm

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803142

ABSTRACT

Global Variance Reduction is useful for radiation protection studies as it allows to compute neutron and gamma doses in large areas with a relatively small computation time, allowing for easier shielding design and optimisation. This paper discusses attempts made to implement the MAGIC method within the TRIPOLI-4[®] Monte-Carlo code. A first attempt has been made to implement the MAGIC method using the Weight Windows technique in the TRIPOLI-4[®] code. However, results were not satisfactory because of long particle history issues as the code may remain stuck during the iterations to calculate the importance map. Therefore, the AMS technique, also present in the TRIPOLI-4[®] code, has been used instead of the Weight Windows technique. This allowed to get rid of the long history issues and the method became reliable, user-friendly, simple to use and efficient in terms of calculation time. The paper shows an application of this technique to a maze made of concrete with a source inside, using both neutron and gamma radiation. The technique is verified by comparing results to those obtained with local variance reduction techniques. In all of the tests made, the method proved to be reliable and efficient.

Keywords: Radiation protection, Global Variance Reduction, AMS, MAGIC, TRIPOLI-4[®]

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Role of variance reduction

Monte-Carlo calculations are needed in radiation protection studies as deterministic calculation schemes are often inadequate for long range and strong attenuation problems. However, Monte-Carlo calculations may suffer from the lack of convergence in interesting areas, usually far from the particle source, as most particles are simulated near the source and few propagate to the areas of interest. Therefore, analogue stochastic calculations may lead to prohibitive calculation times. Variance reduction (VR) is hence introduced to allow particles to propagate to areas of interest without modifying the response function.

1.2. Variance reduction techniques in the TRIPOLI-4[®] code

In the version 12.1 of the TRIPOLI-4[®] [1] general purpose Monte-Carlo code developed by CEA, three variance reduction techniques are implemented :

- The Exponential Transform (ET) algorithm (that also includes splitting and Russian Roulette);
- The Adaptive Multilevel Splitting (AMS) algorithm;
- The Weight Windows (WW) algorithm.

These techniques need an importance map that tells the code in which regions of the phase-space particles are of interest and are to be favoured. This can be done using the CADIS method implemented in

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the TRIPOLI-4[®] code. This implementation is based on the use of the IDT (Integro-Differential Transport) 3D-Method of Short Characteristics module also developed by CEA. However, the CADIS method only allows for local variance reduction. Therefore, for a complete design of the shielding around a nuclear reactor, several calculations are needed, as typically one calculation allows for a convergence on fluxes and doses in a small area. As of version 12.1, no global variance reduction technique is implemented in the TRIPOLI-4[®] code. Furthermore, the IDT solver implemented in TRIPOLI-4[®], is limited to conformal cartesian geometries. The conversion of the geometry to the cartesian one is automatic but care is needed during the definition of the spatial mesh in order to describe the geometry correctly.

2. THE MAGIC METHOD

The MAGIC (Method of Automatic Generation of Importances by Calculation) [2,3] method relies on Monte-Carlo simulations in order to achieve global variance reduction. This method has therefore the potential to improve convergence without the limitations encountered with the CADIS method; this is to say the conversion of the geometry from the Monte-Carlo code to the deterministic solver and the possibly large number of calculations to obtain convergence on large areas.

2.1. Theory

The MAGIC method has been designed for use with the Weight Windows, a common technique among Monte-Carlo codes. Its principle is rather simple: given a mesh cell i , let n_i be the particle density in that cell.

The analogue particle density in this cell is equal to $n_i = \frac{\varphi_i}{v}$ with φ_i being the scalar flux in the cell and v the particle velocity.

In a non-analogue simulation using the Weight Windows technique, the scalar flux should be the same as in an analogue simulation, therefore the analogue particle density can be expressed as follow:

$$n_i = \frac{\varphi_i}{v} \approx \frac{\varphi'_i}{v} = m_i \bar{w}_i \quad (1)$$

with φ'_i being the non-analogue scalar flux, m_i the non-analogue particle density and \bar{w}_i the average particle weight in the cell.

If the centre of the weight window of the cell is set to be proportional to the scalar flux φ_i , the term \bar{w}_i can be written as $\bar{w}_i = k\varphi_i$. The term $m_i \approx \frac{1}{k\varphi_i}$ becomes independent of φ_i and the cell i .

As the statistical uncertainty of the flux in a cell is typically proportional to the inverse of the square root of the particle density: $\sigma_i \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{m_i}}$, this ensures the statistical uncertainty to be almost constant across the cells of the geometry. Hence, the following importance function allows to obtain a constant relative error in all the cells of the geometry:

$$I = \frac{2 \max_{cells} (\varphi_i)}{\varphi_i} \quad (2)$$

The upper and lower weight windows bounds are set to be proportional to the inverse of the importance function, and the 2 factor in the denominator accounts for the typical 5 factor used in Monte-Carlo codes between the upper and the lower weight windows bounds.

As the scalar flux φ_i is the unknown the Monte-Carlo simulation is attempting to calculate, the MAGIC method is based on the following algorithm :

1. Run an analogue Monte-Carlo simulation that calculates the flux on a mesh covering all of the

- geometry.
2. Get the fluxes in each cell in the mesh and calculate the importance in the cell using equation 2. In the cells where no tallies are obtained the minimal flux in the mesh is used.
3. Run a non-analogue Monte-Carlo calculation using the Weight Windows technique and the computed importance map.
4. Repeat steps 3 and 2 until a satisfactory importance map where particles reach all of the geometry is obtained.

In practice, the number of iterations needed to obtain a satisfactory importance map is relatively small (typically less than 10), which allows for a relatively fast computation of the importance map.

2.2. Attempt to implement the algorithm with TRIPOLI-4[®]

As the TRIPOLI-4[®] code enables source biasing by default, the weight of the source particles is already normalised to the importance and therefore equation 2 can be simplified as follows: $I = \frac{1}{\varphi_i}$

An attempt was made to implement the MAGIC algorithm with TRIPOLI-4[®] using the Weight Windows technique available in that code. We observed that in some cases, the calculation may suffer from the problem of long particle histories because of the possible large gradients of fluxes and therefore importances that may be encountered. This problem is due to particles that oversplit because of large differences of importance between adjacent cells, which leads to the calculation being stuck simulating all of the split particles (several decades more particles than the originally predicted). This problem is well known and there are algorithms to tackle it [4]. However, the choice was made to use another variance reduction technique also implemented in the TRIPOLI-4[®] code: the Adaptive Multilevel Splitting (AMS) technique.

3. THE MAGIC METHOD WITH THE ADAPTIVE MULTILEVEL SPLITTING TECHNIQUE

3.1. The AMS technique

The Adaptive Multilevel Splitting VR technique [5,6] has been introduced in TRIPOLI-4[®].11. It requires an importance function as well as a zone of interest. Its principle can be summarised below :

1. An analogue simulation is made;
2. The obtained tracks are sorted using the given importance function;
3. The lowest ranked particles are eliminated and resampled by splitting one of the remaining tracks;
4. Steps 2 and 3 are repeated until enough particles reach the zone of interest.

The AMS technique has been introduced to be used with trivial importance functions such as the inverse of the distance to the zone of interest, but can also be used with an importance function determined with another method such as CADIS. In this paper, we propose to use it combined with the MAGIC method as, with the AMS technique, the importance function is not used for particle weight and population management, but only to sort tracks and particles between themselves, which allows to get rid of the long histories problem observed using the Weight Windows technique. Furthermore, as the importance map during the first few MAGIC iterations can be of very poor quality including possibly large areas unreached by particles and therefore where the importance is set to the maximal value, the AMS algorithm implemented in TRIPOLI-4[®] is smart enough to stop iterating when all particles have the same importance. This prevents the calculation from getting stuck waiting for particles to reach the zone of interest, which may never happen with the low quality importance map in the first MAGIC iterations.

3.2. Implementation of MAGIC/AMS technique

The algorithm described in part 2.1 is implemented within TRIPOLI-4[®] but using the AMS technique instead of the Weight Windows. Each MAGIC iteration is launched using the AMS technique, which iterates on every simulation batch to ensure that enough particles reach the area of interest.

The AMS technique needs not only an importance map but also a zone of interest which is used as stopping criterion for the AMS iterations. This zone of interest can be defined as a physical volume in the geometry. As the MAGIC method is a global variance technique that aims to converge on all the geometry, it would be intuitive to define the entire geometry as the zone of interest. However, doing so would prevent the AMS algorithm from iterating, as all particles would be in the zone of interest on the first AMS iteration. Therefore, the user may define as zone of interest a volume that is placed the farthest away from the particle source. The choice of the zone of interest is not necessarily trivial, but in most cases the user can just select the farthest volume away from the particle source, but still in an area of interest. This allows the AMS algorithm to iterate until enough particles have reached this volume and hence all the geometry, as the transport process is analogue and the chosen volume is the hardest to reach. The AMS algorithm breaks the iteration when the particles have reached the zone of interest, avoiding too much particle tallies in non-interesting areas. However, the user may need to iterate over this choice if the calculation shows that there are volumes harder to reach.

4. APPLICATION TO A CONCRETE MAZE

In this section, the MAGIC/AMS technique is applied to a concrete maze. Neutron and photon transport are studied.

4.1. Presentation of the example

A concrete maze with a source inside is used as a test case. The example is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Concrete maze and the six detectors

Six detectors are scattered around the maze as shown in Figure 1. Detectors 1 to 4 are at the same altitude as the source, while detectors 5 and 6 are placed just above the ground.

4.2. Neutron calculation

In this part, we consider a neutronic source with a fission spectrum.

4.2.1. Importance map calculation

The importance map is calculated using the MAGIC/AMS technique as described in Section 3. The target detector is set to detector 6, as it is the farthest away from the source. The mesh used for the importance map is a regular cartesian mesh with 50 cm cells in the three dimensions.

The calculation was made on 40 CPU and around one hour was needed to perform five iterations (one analogue plus four using the MAGIC/AMS technique) on the importance map. The standard deviation obtained at the end of the first four iterations is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Relative standard deviation of the neutron flux at the end of the first four iterations in the source plane

Figure 2 shows that neutron particles manage to reach all the geometry after 2 iterations on the map.

4.2.2. Convergence on the neutron flux

Two calculations are run on the maze with a neutron source : an analogue calculation and a calculation with the MAGIC/AMS technique. The two calculations are run for 24 hours on 40 CPU. The statistical uncertainty obtained by the two calculations are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Convergence statistics for the neutron calculation

Figure 3 shows that, with the MAGIC/AMS calculation, almost all the cells have a statistical uncertainty

smaller than 10 %. Therefore, global variance reduction has been achieved at relatively low cost.

4.2.3. Comparison of the tallies

In this part, the calculated scores in the six detectors presented in Figure 1 are compared to the classical CADIS/Exponential Transform variance reduction technique of the TRIPOLI-4[®] code. Results, shown in Figure 4, are normalised by setting the flux obtained with the CADIS method to 100 and using the same normalisation factor for the other calculations. Errorbars are 2σ relative standard deviation.

Figure 4. Comparison of the neutron fluxes

Figure 4 shows that the results obtained with the MAGIC/AMS technique are coherent with the analogue and the CADIS/ET technique.

4.3. Photon calculation

In this part, the source is a mono-kinetic 1 MeV photon.

4.3.1. Importance map calculation

The importance map for the photon calculation uses the same mesh as the one used for the neutron calculation. The calculation time for the map is also similar (around one hour on 40 CPU). The convergence at the end of the first four iterations is shown of Figure 5.

Figure 5. Relative standard deviation of the photon flux at the end of the first four iterations in the source plane

Figure 5 shows that more iterations would be necessary for photons to get out of the maze than neu-

trons. However, at the end of the fourth iteration, photons have reached all of the geometry and therefore the importance map generated can be used as it is. The level of precision needed for the importance map calculation is lower than that of a direct flux calculation.

4.3.2. Convergence on the photon flux

Two calculations are run on the maze with a photon source : an analogue calculation and a calculation with the MAGIC/AMS technique. The two calculations are run for 5 days on 40 CPU. The statistical uncertainty obtained by the two calculations is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Convergence statistics for the photon calculation

Figure 6 shows that, with the MAGIC/AMS calculation, more than 80 % of the cells have a statistical uncertainty smaller than 10 %.

4.3.3. Comparison of the tallies

The calculated scores in the six detectors are compared to the CADIS/Exponential Transform variance reduction technique. Results are presented in Figure 7. Errorbars are 2σ relative standard deviation. Note that the analogue calculation gives results only on detector 2 as other detectors are too far from the source to obtain satisfactory convergence without variance reduction.

Figure 7. Comparison of the photon fluxes

Figure 7 shows that the results obtained with the MAGIC/AMS technique are coherent with the analogue and the CADIS/ET technique.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

The implementation of the MAGIC variance reduction technique with the AMS algorithm of TRIPOLI-4[®] managed to achieve global variance reduction for both neutron and photon transport. This method has been applied to a concrete maze and showed satisfactory performance as well as valid result compared to the CADIS/ET variance reduction technique. The MAGIC method is also easy to implement and to use, as it gives good performance even with few iterations and with a coarse spatial mesh.

However, the definition of the target volume for the AMS algorithm may be not trivial in some cases. Therefore, the implementation of an algorithm that searches and updates the target during the MAGIC iterations can be helpful to improve the method for the users.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author wishes to thank the TRIPOLI-4[®] development team (CEA) for allowing him to use the code for this paper, as well as his colleagues Lucas Granger, Emmanuel Lefèvre and Gautier Roland for their help and feedback on this paper.

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